

Research sheet of Turemugo Lab

Volume 4

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新命名、勘误和色彩(2024)

Nomenclatural novelties, errata and colors (2024)

Kun L. Yang (mugoture@gmail.com; College of Forestry and Landscape Architecture, South China Agricultural University, Guangzhou 510642, Guangdong, China)

Jia Y. Lin (mycofloscula@gmail.com; College of Plant Protection, South China Agricultural University, Guangzhou 510642, Guangdong, China)

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Text

Dear colleagues,

This letter presents our following items in and before 2024: (1) Nomenclatural novelties, (2) errata to our work, and (3) defined colors cited in our mycological descriptions.

Nomenclatural novelties

Please see the following Table 1.

▼ **Table 1.** Nomenclatural novelties. Totally, one new family, two new genera, 12 new species, and 54 new combination at species rank are included, ordered by the publication time. Additionally, four newly recorded species in China with Chinese nomenclatural novelties are also attached. (i) later isonym.

Ranks	Scientific names		Authors	Protologues	Current statuses
	Chinese	Latin			
species	面筋高腹菌	<i>Gautieria mianjin</i>	Kun L. Yang, Xiao Liu & Yang Zhu L. Yang	(2023c)	<i>et al.</i> correct name
species	褐果漂泊堪多脆柄菇	<i>Candolleomyces brunneovagabundus</i>	Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Yang Zhu L. Yang	(2023a)	<i>et al.</i> correct name
species	白果漂泊堪多脆柄菇	<i>Candolleomyces albovagabundus</i>	Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Yang Zhu L. Yang	(2023a)	<i>et al.</i> correct name
species	神秘假暗盘菌	<i>Pseudoplectania mystica</i>	Jia Y. Lin, Ling-Han Guo & Kun L. Yang	Lin <i>et al.</i> (2024)	correct name
species	华丽层蘑菇	<i>Hymenagaricus splendidissimus</i>	(Watling) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)	correct name
species	菠萝山黄蘑菇	<i>Xanthagaricus boluoshanensis</i>	Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin, Zhen-Chao Liu & Zhu	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)	correct name

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▼ **Table 1.** (continued)

Ranks	Scientific names		Authors	Protologues	Current statuses
	Chinese	Latin			
species	变色龙黄蘑菇	<i>Xanthagaricus chamaeleontinus</i>	Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin, Yang et al. Zhen-Chao Liu & Zhu (2024b)		al.correct name
species	广州黄蘑菇	<i>Xanthagaricus guangzhouensis</i>	Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Yang et al. Zhu L. Yang (2024b)		al.correct name
species	海氏黄蘑菇	<i>Xanthagaricus heinemannii</i>	Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin, Yang et al. Zhen-Chao Liu & Zhu (2024b)		al.correct name
species	迷你黄蘑菇	<i>Xanthagaricus minimus</i>	Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin, Yang et al. Zhen-Chao Liu & Zhu (2024b)		al.correct name
species	无理黄蘑菇	<i>Xanthagaricus phylononcaeruleus</i>	Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin, Yang et al. Zhen-Chao Liu & Zhu (2024b)		al.correct name
species	网孢黄蘑菇	<i>Xanthagaricus retisporus</i>	Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Yang et al. Zhu L. Yang (2024b)		al.correct name
species	华南农黄蘑菇	<i>Xanthagaricus scauinus</i>	Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Yang et al. Zhu L. Yang (2024b)		al.correct name
genus	燃灯环柄菇属	<i>Candelolepiota</i>	Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Yang et al. Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.correct name
species	燃灯环柄菇 (中华燃灯环柄菇)	<i>Candelolepiota sinica</i>	Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Yang et al. Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.correct name
family	环柄菇科	Lepiotaceae	Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Yang et al. Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.correct name
species	伊氏白环蘑	<i>Leucoagaricus iqbalii</i>	(Asif, Saba & M. Raza) Yang et al. Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.correct name
species	鹅膏状白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus amanitoides</i>	(R.M. Davis & Vellinga) Yang et al. Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.correct name
species	亚马孙白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus amazonicus</i>	(A. Ortiz & Franco-Mol.) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.correct name
species	氨绿白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus ammovirescens</i>	(Bon) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.correct name
species	变橙白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus aurantiovergens</i>	(A. Gennari & Migl.) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.incorrect name (i)
species	巴氏白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus barssii</i>	(Zeller) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.incorrect name (i)
species	邦氏白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus bonii</i>	(A. Caball.) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.correct name
species	肉褐鳞白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus brunneocingulatus</i>	(P.D. Orton) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.incorrect name (i)

... continued below

▼ **Table 1.** (continued)

Ranks	Scientific names		Authors	Protologues	Current statuses
	Chinese	Latin			
species	褐盖白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus brunneodiscus</i>	(A.K. Dutta & K.Yang et al. Acharya) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.correct name
species	苍褶白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus carphophyllus</i>	(Berk. & Broome) KunYang L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.correct name
species	灰根白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus cinereoradicatus</i>	(Boisselet & Migl.) KunYang L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.incorrect name (i)
species	蓝色白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus coerulescens</i>	(Peck) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.correct name
species	拟柏生白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus cupresseoides</i>	(Migl. & Forin) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.incorrect name (i)
species	蓝化白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus cyanescens</i>	(Corriol & Chalange) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.correct name
species	金泪白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus dacrytus</i>	(Vellinga) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.correct name
species	貂皮白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus erminiae</i>	(Consiglio, Setti & Vizzini) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.correct name
species	变绿白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus flavovirens</i>	(J.F. Liang, Zhu L. Yang & J. Xu) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.correct name
species	鳞柄白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus furfuraceipes</i>	(Han C. Wang & Zhu L. Yang) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.correct name
species	戈格白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus gauguei</i>	(Bon & Boiffard) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.incorrect name (i)
species	灰鳞白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus griseosquamosus</i>	(Sysouph. & Thongkl.) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.correct name
species	忽地白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus houaynhangensis</i>	(Sysouphanthong) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.correct name
species	褐绒白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus infuscatus</i>	(Vellinga) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.correct name
species	堇紫白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus ionidicolor</i>	(Bellù & Lanzoni) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.incorrect name (i)
species	鸢尾白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus irinellus</i>	(Chalange) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.correct name
species	老挝白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus laosensis</i>	(Sysouph.) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		al.correct name

... continued below

▼ Table 1. (continued)

Ranks	Scientific names		Authors	Protologues	Current statuses
	Chinese	Latin			
species	紫盖白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus lilaceus</i>	(Singer) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)	Yang et al.	al.correct name
species	褐缘白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus marginatus</i>	(Burl.) Kun L. Yang, Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)	Yang et al.	al.incorrect name (i)
species	黑毛白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus melanotrichus</i>	(Malençon & Bertault) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)	Yang et al.	al.incorrect name (i)
species	土神白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus nzumbae</i>	(C. Heisecke, Carvalho & Neves) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)	A.A. Yang et al.	al.correct name
species	眼斑白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus ophthalmus</i>	(Vellinga) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)	Yang et al.	al.correct name
species	近眼点白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus paraplesius</i>	(Vellinga) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)	Yang et al.	al.correct name
species	假柏生白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus paracupresseus</i>	(Salom, Siquier, Planas & Espinosa) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)	Yang et al.	al.correct name
species	假皮氏白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus pseudopilatianus</i>	(Migl., Rocabruna & Tabarés) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)	Yang et al.	al.incorrect name (i)
species	变紫白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus purpurascens</i>	(T. Guo & Z.W. Ge) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)	Yang et al.	al.correct name
species	焰色白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus pyrrhophaeus</i>	(Vellinga) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)	Yang et al.	al.correct name
species	粉黄白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus rhodelephantinus</i>	(Boisselet & Eyssart.) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)	Yang et al.	al.incorrect name (i)
species	萨宾白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus sabiniae</i>	(Angelini, Justo & Vizzini) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)	Yang et al.	al.correct name
species	始兴白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus shixingensis</i>	(Z.S. Bi & T.H. Li) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)	Yang et al.	al.correct name
species	近浅鳞白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus subcretaceus</i>	(Bon) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)	Yang et al.	al.correct name
species	近层盖白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus subhymenoderma</i>	(Bon & A. Caball.) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)	Yang et al.	al.correct name
species	橘黄白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus tangerinus</i>	(Y. Yuan & J.F. Liang) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)	Yang et al.	al.correct name
species	塔尼娅白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus taniae</i>	(C. Heisecke & Neves) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)	A.A. Yang et al.	al.correct name

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▼ **Table 1.** (continued)

Ranks	Scientific names		Authors	Protologues	Current statuses
	Chinese	Latin			
species	花园白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus viridariorum</i>	(G. Muñoz, A. Caball., Yang <i>et al.</i> Salom & Vizzini) Kun L. (2024a) Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang		<i>al.</i> correct name
genus	大蘑菇属	<i>Macropsalliota</i>	Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024a) Zhu L. Yang		<i>al.</i> correct name
species	大蘑菇 (美洲大蘑菇)	<i>Macropsalliota americana</i>	(Peck) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		<i>al.</i> correct name
species	类糊精孢大蘑菇	<i>Macropsalliota dextrinoidespora</i>	(Z.S. Bi) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		<i>al.</i> correct name
species	拟珠鸡大蘑菇	<i>Macropsalliota holospilota</i>	(Berk. & Broome) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		<i>al.</i> correct name
species	巨孢大蘑菇	<i>Macropsalliota majuscula</i>	(T.K.A. Kumar & Manim.) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		<i>al.</i> correct name
species	珠鸡大蘑菇	<i>Macropsalliota meleagris</i>	(Gray) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		<i>al.</i> correct name
species	尖囊大蘑菇	<i>Macropsalliota mucrocystis</i>	(Pegler) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		<i>al.</i> correct name
species	紫红大蘑菇	<i>Macropsalliota purpureorubra</i>	(Z.S. Bi, T.H. Li & G.Y. Zheng) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		<i>al.</i> correct name
species	亚热带大蘑菇	<i>Macropsalliota subtropica</i>	(Y. Yang, X. Luo & Y.P. Xiao) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		<i>al.</i> correct name
species	热带大蘑菇	<i>Macropsalliota tropica</i>	(A.K. Dutta, Stallman & K. Acharya) Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2024a)		<i>al.</i> correct name
Newly recorded species in China					
	刺猬黄蘑菇	<i>Xanthagaricus erinaceus</i>	(Heinem. & Little Flower) Little Flower, Hosag. & T.K. Abraham		Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
	奇迹黄蘑菇	<i>Xanthagaricus necopinatus</i>	Hosen, T.H. Li & G.M. Gates		Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
	紫鳞黄蘑菇	<i>Xanthagaricus purpureosquamulosus</i>	Sysouph., Thongkl. & K.D. Hyde		Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
	扇纹白鬼伞	<i>Leucocoprinus licmophorus</i>	(Berk. & Broome) Pat.		Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024a)

Errata

To address our academic mysophobia, all articles co-authored by us may have one or more errata, based on the recent discoveries of us or our colleagues. Errata contain corrections and suggestions for any mistake or imprefection in both academic and technical senses. We apologized for the issues regarding these causing inconvenience for you. Please see Table 2 for details.

▼ **Table 2.** Errata to our work, ordered by the publication time. (*) Mistakes and imperfections in books and preprints are expected to be resolved in the next edition or the final publication, and thus are not listed here.

Work	Errata
Yang, K.L. 2019. <i>Mushrooms in the Field</i> . Guangzhou,* China: Guangdong People's Publishing House.	
Yang, K.L., Yang, Z.L. & Wang, P.-M. 2022. Study on the* formation mechanism of ornamentation patterns in spores and pollen as revealed by finite element method. <i>Research Square</i> (preprint) 10.21203/rs.3.rs-2064880/v1.	
Yang, K.L., Yang, Z.L., Zhang, M., Wang, G.S. & Liu, X. 2023.- See Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023b) <i>Gautieria mianjin</i> (Gomphales, Basidiomycota), a new- See Yang (2024) species of false truffle from China. <i>Phytotaxa</i> 594(2):- 119-129.	To resolve the erratum issues, I did obtain a second collection of <i>G. mianjin</i> with kind assistance of my colleagues (Yang 2024), but more collections of a closely related taxon <i>G. xinjiangensis</i> still should be considered. Some colleagues are concerning whether that I create varieties is good for fungal taxonomy, which may cause similar dilemmas like those previously in the <i>Pleurotus ostreatus</i> complex (Li <i>et al.</i> 2020). I am on my way to get more <i>Gautieria</i> collections towards the resolution of these issues.
Yang, K. L., Yang, Z. L., Zhang, M., Wang, G. S. & Liu, X. None 2023. Erratum: Yang, K.L., Yang, Z.L., Zhang, M., Wang, G.S. & Liu, X. (2023) <i>Gautieria mianjin</i> (Gomphales, Basidiomycota), a new species of false truffle from China <i>Phytotaxa</i> 594(2): 119-129. <i>Phytotaxa</i> 597(3): 242-244.	
Yang, K.L. 2023. Towards a standardized expressionNone system of colors in fungal morphological description: color nomenclatural code for description works of specimens in Kun L. Yang's private herbarium (HTBM). <i>Research sheet of Turemugo Lab</i> (posted on Zenodo) 1: 1-5.	

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▼ **Table 2.** (continued)

Work	Errata
Yang, K.L., Lin, J.Y., Li, G.-M. & Yang, Z.L. 2023.- Mushrooms adapted to seawater: two new species- Pages 9 & 15, "anisotropic" of <i>Candolleomyces</i> (Basidiomycota, Agaricales) from China. <i>Journal of Fungi</i> 9(12): 1204.	- See Yang (2024) - "anisotropic" from should be "isotropic" - β - <i>tub</i> sequence of HFJAU1486 was incorrectly reversed, although it has not essential effects on placing <i>Candolleomyces</i>
Lin, J.Y., Guo, L.-H., Li, G.-M., Zhang, M., Xie, D.-C., He, S.-X. & Yang, K.L. 2024. <i>Pseudoplectania mystica</i> (Ascomycota, Pezizales), a new cup fungus with an endophytic habit of a broad range of host plants. <i>Phytotaxa</i> 650(1): 008–022.	None
Yang, K.L. 2024. Erratum to the article <Mushrooms adapted to seawater: two new species of <i>Candolleomyces</i> (Basidiomycota, Agaricales) from China>, and concerns on the taxonomic position of <i>Gautieria mianjin</i> . <i>Research sheet of Turemugo Lab</i> (posted on Zenodo) 2: 1–6.	None
Yang, K.L., Lin, J.Y., Li, G.-M., Liu, Z.-C., Hosen, M.I. & Yang, Z.L. 2024. <i>Heinemannomyces</i> , <i>Hymenagaricus</i> and <i>Xanthagaricus</i> revisited (Basidiomycota, Agaricaceae). <i>Phytotaxa</i> 659(2): 112–164.	- Page 124, the word "designated" in line 7 and the word "shown" in Taxonomy Line 4 should switch places - Fig. 5, bars of n and o are missing: n = 10 μ m, o = 20 μ m
Yang, K.L., Lin, J.Y. & Li, H.-J. 2024. Mushroom poisoning in China (2019–2023)—data listing based on CDC reports. <i>Research sheet of Turemugo Lab</i> (posted on Zenodo) 3(1): 1–39.	- Pages 12 & 30, " <i>Laccaria</i> " should be " <i>Laccaria</i> "
Yang, K.L., Lin, J.Y., Li, G.-M., Li, T.H. & Yang, Z.L. 2024.- Rediscovering <i>Leucoagaricus sinicus</i> , with the recognition of <i>Leucoagaricus</i> and <i>Leucocoprinus</i> as separate genera, and two new genera in Agaricaceae (Basidiomycota). <i>Phytotaxa</i> 676(3): 199–255.	- Abstract, line 8, " <i>Candelolepiota sinicus</i> " should be " <i>Candelolepiota sinica</i> " - 11 new combinations are later isonyms after Migliozi & Donato (2024) (see also Table 1) - Page 244, Morphological key, "c)" missed a half parenthese - Some species names in Table 1 should be in italic, while "cf." should not

Colors

Please see the following Table 3.

▼ **Table 3.** Defined colors following Yang (2023).

Nos.Samples	Color names	Color Codes		Designations
		Chinese	English	
1	甘草褐色	licorice brown	#BFB075	Yang (2023)
2	铜橙色	copper orange	#A56B34	Yang (2023)
3	深豆蔻红色	dark cardamon red	#6B392B	Yang (2023)
4	猫鼬褐色	mongoose brown	#B5A284	Yang (2023)
5	水蓝色	water blue	#D8E5F2	Yang (2023)
6	黄铜褐色	brass brown	#B3794F	Yang (2023)
7	驴褐色	donkey brown	#AC9B87	Yang (2023)
8	灰烬褐色	ash brown	#C8BFB0	Yang (2023)
9	淡紫色	pale violet	#E4D3F8	Yang (2023)
10	浅紫色	light violet	#CFB1F1	Yang (2023)
11	亮紫色	bright violet	#DC9FFF	Yang (2023)
12	中紫色	medium violet	#E0BEF5	Yang (2023)
13	浓紫色	strong violet	#AC5EE2	Yang (2023)
14	深紫色	dark violet	#8C27C1	Yang (2023)
15	污紫色	dirty violet	#C1B2D4	Yang (2023)
16	暗紫色	dull violet	#A38EC0	Yang (2023)
17	纯紫色	pure violet	#5500FF	Yang (2023)
18	乳白色	milky white	#F5F7FA	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023c)
19	沙橙色	sandy orange	#E6CF73	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023c)
20	土橙色	earthy orange	#CF8A45	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023c)
21	木乃伊红色	mummy red	#994D2E	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023c)
22	淡褐色	light brown	#B39966	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023c)
23	纯白色	pure white	#FFFFFF	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023a)
24	姜黄色	ginger yellow	#ECD86C	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023a)
25	枇杷橙色	loquat orange	#F3D390	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023a)
26	桃瓤白色	peach white	#FAF1EC	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023a)
27	饼红色	wafer red	#E4D4CD	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023a)
28	海狸褐色	beaver brown	#9D7B69	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023a)
29	丝绸褐色	silk brown	#CAB7AA	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023a)
30	桑粉色	mulberry pink	#CE5086	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023a)
31	瓷白色	ceramic white	#FEFEFA	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023a)
32	羊毛白色	merino white	#F9F5EC	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023a)
33	藕橙色	lotus-root orange	#F5E9D9	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023a)
34	骨褐色	bone brown	#E3D3C4	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023a)
35	草红色	thatch red	#BEA39C	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023a)
36	檀香红色	sandal red	#BA8A73	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023a)
37	中灰色	medium gray	#E0DEDD	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023a)
38	雾褐色	mist brown	#DCD8C9	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023a)
39	烟灰色	smoke gray	#BCC6C8	Lin <i>et al.</i> (2024)
40	咖啡红色	coffee red	#7B5B4E	Lin <i>et al.</i> (2024)

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▼ Table 3. (continued)

Nos.Samples		Color names		Color Codes	Designations
		Chinese	English		
41		燧石褐色	flint brown	#736960	Lin <i>et al.</i> (2024)
42		煤蓝色	coal blue	#40474D	Lin <i>et al.</i> (2024)
43		暗黑色	dull black	#0B0C0E	Lin <i>et al.</i> (2024)
44		西梅紫色	prune violet	#615074	Lin <i>et al.</i> (2024)
45		夜蓝色	night blue	#525A88	Lin <i>et al.</i> (2024)
46		暗薰衣草紫红色	dull lavender purple	#75647A	Lin <i>et al.</i> (2024)
47		棉籽灰色	cottonseed gray	#BEC0BB	Lin <i>et al.</i> (2024)
48		浓灰色	strong gray	#9D9D9D	Lin <i>et al.</i> (2024)
49		草木灰褐色	wood-ash brown	#A0968A	Lin <i>et al.</i> (2024)
50		深草黄色	dark thatch yellow	#CDC591	Lin <i>et al.</i> (2024)
51		海草褐色	kelp brown	#ACA47E	Lin <i>et al.</i> (2024)
52		燕麦橙色	oat orange	#DFCE7E	Lin <i>et al.</i> (2024)
53		麦粒褐色	barleycorn brown	#9D8F59	Lin <i>et al.</i> (2024)
54		龙猫灰色	chinchilla gray	#7F7E80	Lin <i>et al.</i> (2024)
55		驼褐色	camel brown	#CDC196	Lin <i>et al.</i> (2024)
56		稻草褐色	straw brown	#C4B179	Lin <i>et al.</i> (2024)
57		肉褐色	meat brown	#D7B19D	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
58		檀香褐色	sandal brown	#BA8B70	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
59		深胡椒红色	dark pepper red	#764840	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
60		锈橙色	rust orange	#D79A65	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
61		污蓝色	dirty blue	#A4BAC0	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
62		海军蓝色	cadet blue	#A9B5C3	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
63		暗草黄色	dull thatch yellow	#D3D3B7	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
64		暗粉霜红色	dull blush red	#CDA19C	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
65		茄子粉色	eggplant pink	#714957	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
66		黑加仑紫红色	blackcurrant purple	#422F45	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
67		砖橙色	brick orange	#ECE2B4	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
68		淡米褐色	pale beige brown	#E0CDA5	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
69		淡肉褐色	pale meat brown	#E4C8BB	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
70		草黄色	thatch yellow	#F1ECC5	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
71		亮柚木褐色	bright teak brown	#AF9C6D	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
72		茶橙色	tea orange	#EFDFA0	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
73		污黄铜褐色	dirty brass brown	#B47F5A	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
74		油橙色	butter orange	#F2DF8F	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
75		暗污橙色	dull dirty orange	#EBD087	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
76		亮土橙色	bright earthy orange	#E3B163	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
77		石南褐色	heather brown	#B7AB8F	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
78		暗银灰色	dull silver gray	#A7A6A5	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
79		礁石褐色	reef brown	#CCC2A6	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
80		珍珠木褐色	lacewood brown	#D5B7A1	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
81		南瓜橙色	pumpkin orange	#CEB640	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
82		豆蔻黄色	cardamon yellow	#E0E091	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
83		螺壳白色	conch white	#EFEFF7	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)

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▼ **Table 3.** (continued)

Nos.Samples	Color names		Color Codes	Designations	
	Chinese	English			
84		紫藤紫色	wisteria violet	#C5BBDC	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
85		洋桔梗紫色	lisianthus violet	#846994	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
86		暗丝绸褐色	dull silk brown	#C3B3A6	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
87		金橙色	golden orange	#E4CB4E	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
88		沙漠橙色	desert orange	#E8D7B0	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
89		猪白色	pig white	#FDF7F2	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
90		鸡肉橙色	chicken orange	#F8DCC9	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
91		风滚草橙色	tumbleweed orange	#E8B28F	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
92		大麦褐色	barley brown	#E6D1B5	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
93		陈皮橙色	tangerine-peel orange	#CD6425	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
94		亚麻褐色	linen brown	#E6DECB	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
95		焦糖橙色	caramel orange	#DB8E37	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
96		乳黄色	milky yellow	#FFF07A	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
97		沙滩黄色	beach yellow	#F9F3C9	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
98		滨螺蓝色	periwinkle blue	#CDCFE5	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
99		紫檀红色	rosewood red	#78545C	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
100		淡滨螺蓝色	pale periwinkle blue	#C9D4E6	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
101		暗鸽蓝色	dull pigeon blue	#A9B5C3	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
102		淡骨褐色	pale bone brown	#E7D5C7	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
103		泥潭褐色	mire brown	#B89F89	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
104		枯叶绿色	withered green	#D5DCB7	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
105		脏绿色	muck green	#92A890	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
106		污草红色	dirty thatch red	#BFA5A5	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
107		暗草红色	dull thatch red	#B29B9C	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
108		污乳褐色	dirty milky brown	#B7A48D	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
109		锆白色	zircon white	#F3F5FD	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
110		石膏白色	alabaster white	#F9F9F9	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
111		布褐色	cotton brown	#D2CAAD	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
112		狮橙色	lion orange	#EFD871	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
113		樱桃木褐色	cherrywood brown	#DAB697	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
114		月黄色	moon yellow	#FAF9AA	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
115		魔黄色	mana yellow	#F7F57E	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
116		昏橙色	dusk orange	#CEAD64	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
117		阴天蓝色	overcast blue	#D6DBE7	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
118		污紫藤紫色	dirty wistaria violet	#C5BCCC	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
119		牛排紫红色	steak purple	#877280	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
120		污天蓝色	dirty sky blue	#BED5DB	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
121		沙绿色	sand green	#B2C4B5	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
122		水墨绿色	ink green	#9DB1A7	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
123		淡石板蓝色	pale slate blue	#688D99	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
124		大麦橙色	barley orange	#E4C8A4	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
125		淡褐色	pale brown	#E3DECC	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
126		暗丝绸红色	dull silk red	#BBA8A2	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)

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▼ **Table 3.** (continued)

Nos.Samples	Color names		Color Codes	Designations	
	Chinese	English			
127		鸭血红色	duck blood red	#564843	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
128		泥褐色	muddy brown	#BD936D	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
129		咖啡豆褐色	coffee bean brown	#483625	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
130		湿沙黄色	wet sand yellow	#CCC796	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
131		淡污橙色	pale dirty orange	#FAF4E3	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
132		暗橙色	dull orange	#E3C4A3	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
133		布丁橙色	pudding orange	#FFE8A3	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
134		淡乳橙色	pale milky orange	#FFEDA2	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
135		金鸡菊橙色	goldenrod orange	#F9D873	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
136		亮焦糖橙色	bright caramel orange	#EB9300	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
137		暗金橙色	dull golden orange	#D8B77B	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
138		深树莓红色	dark raspberry red	#B96F62	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024a)
139		亮石南褐色	bright heather brown	#B9AB8D	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024a)
140		浅豆蔻绿色	light cardamon green	#ECFA9D	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024a)
141		淡豆蔻黄色	pale cardamon yellow	#F7F9D4	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024a)
142		淡土橙色	pale earthy orange	#F8E8C4	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024a)
143		浅柚木褐色	light teak brown	#BCAC84	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024a)
144		柚木黄色	teak yellow	#CDC79B	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024a)
145		浅豆蔻黄色	light cardamon yellow	#E9E9AD	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024a)

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